

METHOD AND ALGORITHM FOR NUMERICAL SOLUTION OF BOUNDARY VALUE PROBLEM FOR ONE-DIMENSIONAL LINEAR DIFFERENTIAL EQUATION

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Introduction. At present, mathematical models of many physical processes are written by parabolic differential equations, including problems of oil, gas and water filtration in porous media, heat removal problems, etc.

Targeted research aimed at studying the processes of groundwater filtration is widely conducted around the world. One of the most important hydrogeological processes is groundwater filtration or geofiltration, which is a gravity flow of water through porous or fractured media. Groundwater movement is mainly carried out by geofiltration [2]. Analytical solutions of such problems in generalized cases are very difficult to find. That's why we use a range of methods to solve them.

At present, it is widely used to solve various problems on a computer by the numerical method, displaying the results obtained in 2D and 3D graphics. Such representation of calculation results is important in the study and analysis of processes.

Mathematical model. It is necessary to solve a boundary problem imposed on the following one-dimensional linear differential equation using numerical methods. To simplify, consider the area considered in the boundary value problem. $G\{0 < x < 1, 0 \leq t \leq 1\}$

Then we can write the mathematical model of the boundary value problem as follows:

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial x^2} + 3ke^{3kxt}(x - 3kt^2) \quad (1)$$

In the general case, the initial and boundary conditions can be written as follows:

$$P(x, t) = \phi(x), \quad t = 0; \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{cases} -\frac{dP}{dx}\Big|_{x=0} = \alpha(P_A - P), & x = 0; \\ \frac{dP}{dx}\Big|_{x=1} = \alpha(P_B - P), & x = 1; \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Here:

- P - the desired function, the value of which is calculated;
- $P_A, P_B - P$ - limit value of the function;

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{border fixed} \\ 1, & \text{border is not fixed} \end{cases}$$

To check the correctness of the results obtained and the adequacy of the mathematical model, we obtain an analytical solution of the boundary value problem as follows:

$$P(x, t) = e^{-3kxt}$$

Then the boundary and initial conditions are as follows:

$$\begin{cases} P(x,0) = 1, \\ P(0,t) = 1, \\ P(1,t) = e^{3kt}, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$f(x,t) = 3ke^{3kt}(x - 3kt^2) \quad (5)$$

For the numerical solution of the boundary value problem, we replace the field with the following discrete field. To do this, we construct the following grid:

$$\Omega_{h\tau} = \left\{ x = ih, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, N, \quad h = \frac{1}{N}, \quad t_j = j\tau, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, N_0, \quad \tau = \frac{1}{N_0} \right\}$$

To solve the problem numerically in this discrete domain, we use the finite difference method based on the variable directional scheme. In this method, the time layer is implemented in τ steps. The finite difference equation can be written in operator form by discarding the index i as follows:

$$\frac{P^{k+1} - P^k}{\Delta\tau} = \Lambda P^{k+1} + f(x,t). \quad (6)$$

In this case the system of finite difference equations in the time layer $l + 1$ has the following form.

$$a_i P_{i-1} - b_i P_i + c_i P_{i+1} = -d_i, \quad (7)$$

Here:

$$a_i = \frac{1}{h^2}; \quad b_i = \frac{2}{h^2} + \frac{1}{\Delta\tau}; \quad c_i = \frac{1}{h^2}; \quad (8)$$

$$d_i = \frac{1}{\Delta\tau} P_i^l + 3ke^{3kx}(x - 3kt^2), \quad (9)$$

The progonka method is used to solve the finite difference system (in the time layer $l + 1$). Its numerical solution by the progonka method is determined by the following formula:

$$P_i = A_i P_{i+1} + B_i \quad (i = n - 1, \dots, 1); \quad (10)$$

Here: A_i, B_i the progonka coefficients, which are determined by the following formulas:

$$A_i = \frac{c_i}{b_i + a_i A_{i-1}}; \quad B_i = \frac{a_i B_{i-1} + d_i}{b_i + a_i A_{i-1}}; \quad (11)$$

The initial values of the progonka coefficients A_0, B_0 are determined from the boundary conditions. For the first boundary condition in the general case (3) follows:

$$A_0 = \frac{b_1 - 4c_1}{a_1 - (3 - 2\Delta x)c_1}; \quad B_0 = \frac{d_1}{a_1 - (3 - 2\Delta x)c_1}. \quad (12)$$

For the specific example used above (4), the value of the function is determined by the formula in the right limit.

$$P_N^l = e^{3kt}; \quad A_0 = 0; \quad B_0 = 1. \quad (13)$$

Pic. 1 Block diagram of the algorithm for solving the boundary value problem of a one-dimensional parabolic equation

Algorithm for the numerical solution of the boundary value problem:

1. Start.
2. N, h, nt, x, k assigning a value to variables.
3. P - enter initial value of function. $(i=1, 2, \dots, N,)$
4. a_i, b_i, c_i, d_i calculation of coefficients of finite difference equation.
5. A_0, B_0 set boundary conditions.
6. A_i, B_i calculate progonka coefficients. $(i=2, \dots, N-1,)$
7. P_n calculate the value of the function. $(\text{time } j=1, 2, \dots, nt)$
8. Derivation of the result in the form of a numerical solution and a three-dimensional graph.
9. End.

A mathematical model and an algorithm for this equation have been developed. The results were obtained in the MatLab programming environment:

Pic. 2. Exact solution of 2D graphics (k=0.5)

Pic.3. Numerical solution of 2D-graph (k=0.5)

Pic.4. The exact and numerical solution varies in the cross section along the x

Conclusion. In conclusion, we can say that the greater the number of points, the fewer errors, that is, the numerical solution approaches the exact one.

Numerical results and two-dimensional graphics are presented in the created software.

The constructed mathematical models and the computational algorithms that implement them, as well as software tools, serve as the basis for solving problems in the class of water filtration processes in porous media.

References:

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